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Bionomics and geographical distribution of *Eugnosta* Hübner, [1825] species in Hungary (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae)

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Abstract. The first study in Hungary examines the bionomy and geographical distribution of *Eugnosta* Hübner, [1825] species living in the country. It shows the sites of *Eugnosta lathoniana* (Hübner, [1799–1800]) and *Eugnosta magnificana* (Rebel, 1914) on maps. Based on more than a hundred years of data, it records the flight time and preferred habitats of the adults. The last specimen of *Eugnosta magnificana* was collected in Hungary 86 years ago, so it has likely disappeared from the country.

Keywords. Lepidoptera, Tortricidae, *Eugnosta lathoniana*, *Eugnosta magnificana*, area, ecology, Hungary.

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Zusammenfassung. Die erste Studie in Ungarn untersucht die Bionomie und die geografische Verbreitung der im Land vorkommenden Arten von *Eugnosta* Hübner, [1825]. Die Fundorte von *Eugnosta lathoniana* (Hübner, [1799–1800]) und *Eugnosta magnificana* (Rebel, 1914) werden auf Karten dargestellt. Auf Grundlage von Daten aus mehr als hundert Jahren werden die Flugzeiten und bevorzugten Lebensräume der erwachsenen Tiere erfasst. Für *Eugnosta lathoniana* sind in Ungarn die meisten Funde aus dem Ballungsraum Budapest (Hauptstadt) bekannt. Dabei handelt es sich meist um alte Beobachtungen, die 50–100 Jahre alt sind. Die meisten der erfassten Orte wurden inzwischen überbaut oder vollständig umgestaltet und sind daher heute verschwunden. Die Art kommt in Ungarn heute nur mehr sehr lokal vor und ist im Rückzug begriffen. Populationen haben nur in geschützten Gebieten, zum Beispiel in Natura 2000 Gebieten oder Landschaftsschutzgebieten überlebt. Das letzte Exemplar von *Eugnosta magnificana* wurde vor 86 Jahren in Ungarn gesammelt, sodass man annehmen muss, dass die Art wahrscheinlich heute verschwunden ist. Sie ist weder im ungarischen Roten Buch noch in der nationalen Liste der geschützten Arten aufgeführt. Man muss davon ausgehen, dass sie von den ungarischen Naturschutzbehörden und Lepidopterologen übersehen wurde.

Introduction

From Hungary, only two species of *Eugnosta* Hübner, [1825] have been identified so far: *Eugnosta lathoniana* (Hübner, [1799–1800]) and *Eugnosta magnificana* (Rebel, 1914). Their geographic distribution and bionomics have not yet been studied by Hungarian researchers. The author has revised the major Hungarian collections and faunistic publications.

This study describes the geographical distribution patterns of *Eugnosta* species in Hungary, the flight times of the adults, the larval food plants and the preferred habitats. Special emphasis is given to the status of *Eugnosta magnificana* populations.

Results

Eugnosta Hübner, [1825]

The genus is rich in species, with more than 100 species so far described from the Holarctic, Neotropical, and Afrotropical regions. According to Razowski (2009) 13 species occur in the Palearctic and of these four are found in Europe. They fly in one or two generations per year, mainly in dry or mesophilic grassland communities, avoiding closed forests. They can be collected by light in the evening and at night. Little is known about the life history of the larvae and the food plants. They hibernate as larvae.

Eugnosta lathoniana (Hübner, [1799–1800])

[*Tortrix*] *lathoniana* Hübner, [1799–1800], Samml. eur. Schmett., Tortrices, pl. 30, fig., 189. Locus typicus: „Europe”.
Type of specimen: unknown.

References: Danilevsky & Kuznetsov 1968, Fazekas 2002, Kennel 1921, Pastorális. & Buschmann 2018, Petrich 2001, Razowski J. 2001, 2009, Sinev 2019.

Geographical distribution: A western Palaearctic species. Occurs from the Urals, through the Caucasus, in Asia Minor, Central and Southern Europe, west to Portugal, and in North Africa. Local, sometimes fragmented populations are known everywhere. Note: Sinev (2019) catalogues the species as having an extremely limited distribution in Russia. I made the map based on Sinev (see on Text-fig. 1.).

Text-fig. 1. Distribution *E. lathoniana* in Russia

Confirmed localities in Hungary: Aggtelek (Vörös-tó), Budafok, Budaörs (Csiki-hegyek), „Budapest” (old data, habitats partially incorporated or destroyed: Hármashatár-hegy, Kamaraerdő, Márton-hegy, Sas-hegy, Széchenyi-hegy), Budatétény, Dobogókő, Dömsöd (Apajpuszta), Fót-Csomád, Fót (Somlyó-hegy), Gyöngyös, Hódmezővásárhely, Jánoshalma, Jászberény, Kaposvár, Nagykáta, Nagytétény, Ohat, Öskü, Pákozd, Pécel, Pécs, Kunpeszér, Szentendre, Szeged (Szőreg), Újszász, Vác.

Bionomics: According to Razowski (2009) the moth has been collected in May and June, sometimes in July. However, the flight time of Hungarian adults is significantly different. Based on both examined specimens and data from publications in Hungary, there are two generations: The first from early May to June and the second from July to early September. September specimens are also known from Russia (Astrachan: det. & photo A. Ponomarev).

We do not have any data on the larva or the food plant in Hungary. Savchuk & Kajgorodova (2017) succeeded in clarifying the previously unknown larval biology of this species for the first time in Crimea. They found the caterpillar living in the lower part of the stalk of a thistle (*Carduus hamulosus*). This plant is well known in Hungary and is mainly found on steppe meadows and in rocky grasslands (Király 2009), primarily in the lowland and south-eastern parts of the country, near the Romanian border, where very few Lepidoptera surveys have been conducted. It also occurs in many mountain and hilly areas; the geographical distribution in Hungary is shown in Figure 4. There are five potential *Carduus* species in Hungary.

Habitat in Hungary: Dry grasslands, pastures, fallows, dolomitic and limestone rocky grasslands, karstic forest margins, dry forest clearings. Altitude: Occurs from the lowlands to 700 m in the mountains. In Asia Minor (Karaman, Merkez, det. et photo: Ö. Koçak) and the Iberian Peninsula (leg. et det.: F. Graf), it reaches altitudes of 1000–1200 m.

Notes: In Hungary, most of the sites are known from the Budapest (capital) agglomeration. These are mostly old observations, 50–100 years old and the majority of the recorded places have been built up or completely transformed and have disappeared. The species is highly localized and in regression in the country. Populations survive only in protected areas, for example in Natura 2000 sites or protected landscape areas.

Eugnosta magnificana (Rebel, 1914)

Euxanthis magnificana Rebel, 1914, Dt. ent. Z. Iris 28.: 273. Locus typicus: China, Kul'ja.

Synonym: *Tortrix margaritana* Hübner, [1813], *Tortrix norvichiana* Hübner, [1817]

References: Danilevsky & Kuznetsov 1968, Kennel 1921, Pastorális. & Buschmann 2018, Petrich 2001, Razowski J. 2001, 2009, Sinev 2019.

Text-fig. 2. Distribution of *E. magnificana* in Russia

Geographical distribution: It has been recorded in the meridional Palaearctic regions, from China, Mongolia, and central Asia to southern France, but is a local and highly fragmented species. Sinev (2019) catalogues the species as having an extremely limited distribution in Russia. I made the map based on Sinev (see Text-fig. 2.).

Confirmed localities in Hungary: Budafok [1904], Budapest [1877] (Kamaraerdő, Káposztásmegyer [1936], Sas-hegy [1893], Széchenyi-hegy [1903], Újpest [1903]), Pápa (1892). The first sighting in Hungary was in 1877 and the last in 1936. Consequently, it seems that nobody has collected or photographed it in Hungary in the 86 years since.

Bionomy: Larvae and food plants are not known. Adults were collected in Hungary from May to August. According to Razowski (2009) rarely collected in September. Possibly two generations of adults.

Habitat in Hungary: Most of the known and very old habitats in Hungary are in Budapest. A significant part of them has been destroyed, built up and can no longer be reconstructed. Only one relatively natural habitat has survived – in the nature conservation area: Sas-hegy.

The "Buda Sas-hegy Nature Reserve" belongs to the Danube-Ipoly National Park. The 30 acres (120,000 m²) area on the top of the hill (257 m) was placed under protection in 1958. It was one of the first nature reserves in Hungary, protecting the limestone landscape and its special flora and fauna. Sas-hegy is a small dolomite hill, the steep dolomite slopes are covered with the original vegetation of dolomite grassland, dominated by *Festuca pallens* and *Carex humilis* (Zólyomi 1958). Probable habitats of occurrence of this species should be sought: closed rock grassland; endemic grassland of *Seslerietum sadlerianae*; dry open rock grassland on steep southern slope (*Seseli leucospermi-Festucetum pallentis*); mosaic grassland, shrubs around; large grassy area on a moderate eastern slope. According to Bölöni et al. (2011) of typical habitats: Calcareous open rocky grasslands, closed rocky grasslands, calcareous rocky steppes (see in Fig. 10).

Notes: *Eugnosta magnificana* is likely to be extinct in Hungary. It is neither listed in the Hungarian Red Book nor the national list of protected species; it has escaped the attention of Hungarian conservation authorities and lepidopterozoology researchers.

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Figs 1–5. 1. *Eugnosta lathoniana*: head in top view, wing pattern; 2. Schematic distribution of the potential foodplant *Carduus hamulosus* in Hungary; 3. Confirmed localities in Hungary; 4. Habitat in South Hungary, Mecsek Mts., Pécs; 5. Habitat in Bakony Mts., Öskü. Habitat of species: Dry grasslands, pastures, fallows, dolomitic and limestone rocky grasslands, karstic forest margins, dry forest clearings.

Figs 6–10. *Eugnosta magnificana*: head in top view, wing pattern; **7.** The first sighting in Hungary was in 1877 and the last was in 1936 in Budapest (Újpest). **8.** Confirmed localities in Hungary; **9.** The "last" observation site in Hungary in 1893 in Budapest, on the "Sas-hegy"; **10.** The typical habitat of the species is the "Sas-hegy" in Budapest. Sas-hegy is a small dolomite hill, the steep dolomite slopes are covered with the original vegetation of dolomite grassland, dominated by *Festuca pallens* and *Carex humilis*. For a detailed description, see the text. (Fig. 10: ©<https://www.sashegyvedo.hu/legifotok/>)

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